

Generation of Terahertz Frequencies Using Potentially NLO active Organic High Quality Single Crystals of BNA and DAST - An Indigenous Approach

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Abstract

The field of generation and detection of Terahertz (THz) frequencies has attracted worldwide attention since many important molecules such as proteins, pharmaceuticals, explosives, narcotic drugs, etc., exhibit their characteristic fingerprints in this region of the electromagnetic spectrum [1]. However, developing proper sources and detectors in this region has been a serious problem and attempts are being made to narrow down the gap between the optic and electronic region which is known as “THz gap” in the electromagnetic spectrum [2-3]. In coming decades, a lot more innovative research is expected in this area and the continuing effort to identify more compact, powerful sources in THz range. In this direction, BNA and DAST material (NLO coefficient of 234 and 1100 pm/V respectively) has been synthesized and high-quality twin free single crystals were grown by slow evaporation solution technique. The grown single crystals were potentially used to generate THz waves in the frequency range (0.2-3 THz).

Figure 1. Photograph of indigenously grown (a)BNA and (b) DAST Single crystals (c) Amplitude spectra of THz waves generated from BNA single crystals of various solvents.

Keywords: Organic Materials, Crystal Growth, Terahertz Generation and Detection

References

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